

Enhancing QDTrack with Self-Attention in Autonomous Driving Environments

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Abstract: Reliable and safe navigation of self-driving cars requires multi-object tracking algorithms to estimate the trajectories of moving objects on the road. The performance of tracking algorithms can be improved by optimizing each component of the detector-tracker pipeline. A valuable method to improve detectors is exploiting attention mechanisms, which imitate how humans find salient regions in a scene. In this paper, we have integrated self-attention mechanisms into Faster R-CNN, the detector included in QDTrack, a state-of-the-art tracker that follows the tracking-by-detection paradigm. We have evaluated the performance of the enhanced multi-object tracking system on the BDD100K dataset. Results show that integrating attention mechanisms into the detector improves QDTrack tracking performance, particularly in terms of mMOTA, at the cost of increased inference time and model complexity. The results highlight an explicit accuracy–efficiency trade-off.

1 INTRODUCTION

The development of self-driving cars promises to improve people’s and goods’ mobility by reducing or preventing accidents, decreasing fuel consumption and emissions, avoiding traffic jams, and increasing access to transport for mobility-impaired groups (Carletti et al., 2024).

To guarantee safe navigation in the real world, autonomous vehicles (AVs) must perceive the surrounding environment, predict the behaviors of other road users, and make real-time decisions.

The two main approaches adopted to develop self-driving systems are the modular pipeline and the end-to-end pipeline. The modular approach breaks down the complex driving problem into the tasks of perception, localization, planning, and control, each of which is solved by one or more sub-systems. On the other hand, end-to-end systems map sensory inputs to driving actions with a single deep neural network (Tampuu et al., 2020).

The main advantage of modular systems, which makes them the current state of the art in industry, is that each module’s output is human-interpretable,

allowing intervention in case of failure.

In such systems, the perception process occurs earlier in the pipeline and influences the planning and control tasks. In particular, reliable path planning and navigation of AVs require accurate multi-object tracking (MOT) algorithms, which estimate the trajectories of moving objects on the road, such as pedestrians and other vehicles, possibly collecting compact feature representations (Greco et al., 2025).

Multi-object tracking is a challenging problem because of appearance variations of the objects caused by sensor noise, partial or total occlusions caused by complex interactions between objects, variable weather or lighting conditions, computational time requirements, and so on. In the case of autonomous driving, MOT is even more complex because images are acquired in real time by a camera that is moving with the vehicle. The difficulties in predicting the apparent motion of stationary agents or their real motion on the road, missing detections in some frames due to occlusions, and the difficulties in object association due to appearance-based re-identification are some of the problems that complicate the MOT task in autonomous driving (Cao et al., 2024).

MOT systems can be divided into three groups depending on their structures: tracking by detection (TBD), joint detection and tracking, and transformer-based tracking (Guo et al., 2022b). The TBD paradigm has been the most adopted so far, while

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transformer-based solutions represent a new and promising approach to the MOT problem.

The modular architecture of TBD systems has the intrinsic advantage that performance can be improved by optimizing each component of the detector-tracker pipeline (Gragnaniello et al., 2023), while transformer-based multi-object tracking has the advantage of exploiting self-attention to gather global contextual information (Guo et al., 2022b).

The contribution of this paper is to exploit the advantages of both tracking-by-detection and transformer-based MOT systems by integrating self-attention mechanisms into the detector of a state-of-the-art tracking-by-detection MOT, and investigate how this change impacts the tracking performance in the autonomous driving scenario.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 briefly reports the adoption of attention mechanisms in object detection and multi-object tracking, Section 3 describes the way attention mechanisms have been integrated into the detector of the MOT system, Section 4 describes the experimental protocol, and Sections 5 and 6 report and discuss the results of the modified system compared to the baseline one. Eventually, in the Conclusions, we summarize the work and outline our future investigations.

2 RELATED WORKS

The performance of tracking-by-detection systems depends on many factors and is highly influenced by the detection performance (Ciaparrone et al., 2020). In the autonomous driving scenario, different combinations of detectors and trackers were evaluated on the BDD100K dataset, and it has been shown that the best configuration of 22 evaluated was the pipeline combining ConvNext as a detector and QDTrack’s tracking module (Gragnaniello et al., 2023).

A valuable method to improve the performance of a detector is applying attention mechanisms, which have been proposed to imitate how humans find salient regions in scenes. Channel and spatial attention are the most applied attention mechanisms in computer vision. Channel attention identifies the most relevant features in the feature map, whereas spatial attention identifies the feature map’s regions where the key information is located. These mechanisms are implemented as a dynamic weight adjustment process based on features of the input image (Guo et al., 2022a).

Examples of the beneficial effect of including attention mechanisms in a detector are (Zhou et al., 2021; Wang and He, 2022), where spatial attention

and deformable convolution networks (DCNs) were used to improve the Faster-RCNN detector in the context of autonomous driving (Zhou et al., 2021), and the Mask RCNN detector in the context of apple segmentation (Wang and He, 2022). One of the advantages highlighted in (Zhou et al., 2021) was that small objects and occluded objects were better detected by the enhanced Faster-RCNN.

Papers focused on the MOT problem have exploited attention mechanisms to improve the performance of a detector and then of the tracking system. In (Li et al., 2024), the authors improved the perception capabilities of ultra-low-altitude agricultural drones by replacing the traditional Faster R-CNN used in the QDTrack architecture (Fischer et al., 2023) with a modified version of Mask R-CNN that integrated spatial attention mechanisms and deformable convolution networks. These modifications enhanced the performance of the MOT, which surpassed the original QDTrack.

In the context of multi-object pedestrian tracking, QDTrack was modified by introducing into the Resnet-50 backbone network a lightweight attention module, which combined both channel and spatial attention (Zhou et al., 2023). This change improved the overall detection performance of the network and then the tracking performance.

3 METHOD

In this section, we present the proposed method in two different subsections. Firstly, the QDTrack algorithm is detailed, which is crucial to clearly present our contribution regarding the integration of the attention mechanism and the principal parameters. Secondly, we present the contribution itself, describing the transformer module implemented.

3.1 QDTrack

Quasi-Dense Tracking (QDTrack) (Fischer et al., 2023; Pang et al., 2021) is a multi-object tracking method consisting of three key components: object detection, quasi-dense similarity learning, and object association with track management. It relies on an appearance-only tracking mechanism, which uses visual features extracted from detected objects to match.

It is based on a multi-task neural network with two heads: one detects the objects providing bounding boxes and classes, while the other computes an appearance-based feature vector used for matching blobs and objects. The detector includes an additional embedding head that generates a feature vec-

tor for each bounding box that is used to compute the similarity between the predicted bounding boxes and the objects present in the scene. The detection head densely samples hundreds of candidate regions across frames, generating a large number of bounding boxes. Each of these candidate regions is mapped to an embedding space by the embedding head. During training, using a contrastive loss, the correct representation of each detected bounding box is learned, so that similar objects are mapped close to each other and different objects are as far apart as possible.

To associate predicted bounding boxes and tracked objects in the scene, a bi-directional softmax function is employed in the feature embedding space. In terms of track management, QDTrack removes objects after a configurable number of frames, new objects with a high confidence score are immediately tracked, whereas new objects with lower scores are tracked if they remain matched for a certain number of frames.

The training process requires the selection of two types of frames: **key frames** and **reference frames**. A **key frame** is one of those frames used to sample object regions and compute embeddings, while a **reference frame** is a frame temporally adjacent to a key frame used to establish object associations. By matching regions between the key and reference frames, the model learns to associate objects across frames, forming the foundation of quasi-dense similarity learning. This design ensures that the embeddings are discriminative and capable of capturing both object appearance and inter-frame associations effectively.

3.2 Integrating Spatial Attention in the QDTrack Detector

The original implementation of QDTrack uses Faster R-CNN as the detector for object detection (Ren et al., 2016). Faster R-CNN comprises ResNet-50 as the backbone to extract features from input images, Feature Pyramid Network as the neck to combine features from both deeper and earlier layers, a Region Proposal Network head to generate candidate regions with various scales and aspect ratios, and a RoI head that performs the final classification and bounding box regression.

ResNet-50 consists of one stem layer, which reduces spatial resolution while extracting basic image features, and four bottleneck residual blocks, which perform convolution on the spatial dimensions to extract features that capture patterns like edges, textures, and object parts (He et al., 2016). We modified ResNet-50’s architecture by exploiting attention

mechanisms to improve the performance of the backbone and, as a consequence, of the entire tracking system.

Attention mechanisms learn weights that determine the relevance of the elements in the original feature maps computed by the backbone. In particular, residual blocks were enhanced by adding transformer attention modules and deformable convolutional networks, as shown in Figure 1. The 3×3 convolution of the residual block was replaced by a 3×3 deformable convolution whose output was processed by the transformer attention module. In particular, as proposed in (Zhu et al., 2019), the last two residual blocks of ResNet-50 were substituted with an attended residual block. The feature maps computed by the modified ResNet-50 were used as the input of FPN for multi-scale feature extraction.

Each feature map inputted into an attended residual block is transformed into **query**, **key**, and **value** representations, which are used by the self-attention mechanism to capture relationships among the input elements and detect the most relevant parts of the input. In self-attention, the key and the query are modeled from the same set of features.

Both the output of the transformer module and the DCN can be described using the generalized attention formulation proposed in (Zhu et al., 2019). Each output feature y_q is computed as the linear combination with learnable weights of the outputs of multiple attention functions. Let q be the index of a query element with content z_q and k be the index of a key element with content x_k , y_q is given by eq. 1, where M is the number of attention heads, Ω_q is the supporting key region for the query, $A_m(q, k, z_q, x_k)$ are the attention weights of the m -th attention head, and W_m and W'_m are learnable weights.

$$y_q = \sum_{m=1}^M W_m \left[\sum_{k \in \Omega_q} A_m(q, k, z_q, x_k) \odot W'_m x_k \right], \quad (1)$$

Transformer modules and DCNs differ in the way the attention weights are computed. In (Dai et al., 2019), it has been proposed to define the attention weights of a transformer module as the combination of four terms, named attention factors, as shown in eq. 2. The attention factors are ϵ_1 , which is sensitive to the query and the key content, ϵ_2 , which accounts for the query content and the relative position between the query and the key, ϵ_3 , which is sensitive only to the key content, and ϵ_4 which only accounts for the relative position.

$$A_m^{\text{Transformer}}(q, k, z_q, x_k) \propto \exp \left(\sum_{j=1}^4 \epsilon_j \right) \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: Attended residual block.

Deeming deformable convolution as a special case of self-attention, the attention weights are determined as in eq. 3 where G is a bilinear interpolation kernel, p_m is a predetermined positional offsets, and $w_m^\top x_q$ is a learnable transformation of the query content. In the case of DCNs, the attention factors are query content and relative position.

$$A_m^{\text{dcn}}(q, k, x_q) = G(k, q + p_m + w_m^\top x_q) \quad (3)$$

4 EXPERIMENTAL PROTOCOL

In this section, we first present the online benchmark used for performance evaluation and the adopted metrics. Then, we describe the training procedure implemented to fine-tune the pretrained model after integrating the attention module. Finally, we describe the ablation study that highlights the contribution of our choices to the achieved performance level.

4.1 Dataset

The proposed method was evaluated on the BDD100K dataset (Yu et al., 2020). It’s a large-scale dataset of driving scenes consisting of 100K annotated video clips particularly suitable to evaluate object detection and multi-object tracking algorithms. The video sequences were recorded in highly populated cities of the United States of America and show a heterogeneity of scene types, including highways and city streets, weather conditions, and times of day. The dataset is organized into different subsets designed to serve as benchmarks for different tasks, such as object detection, image segmentation, and object tracking.

The BDD100K Object Detection subset is made up of 100K images, which are the frames at the 10th second of each video. These images have a size of 1280x720 and are annotated with bounding boxes and 10 categories of objects: car, pedestrian, truck, bus, bike, rider, motorcycle, train, traffic sign, and traffic light. The 100K images are divided into training set (70K), validation set (10K), and testing set (20K), but

only training and validation sets are publicly available.

The BDD100K Multi-Object Tracking subset includes 2000 out of the 100K video clips divided into training (1400 videos), validation (200 videos), and test set (400 videos). Each video lasts approximately 40 seconds and is annotated at 5 fps, resulting in approximately 200 frames per video. The annotated frames included bounding boxes and associated attributes (Occluded, Truncated, Crowd) for each tracked object. In this paper, the experimental evaluation was performed using the validation set of the BDD100K MOT subset, while the test set is excluded because its annotations are not publicly available.

4.2 Evaluation Metrics

We exploited different metrics adopted in international competitions on object detection and tracking to evaluate both detectors’ and trackers’ performance.

The detector performance is evaluated in terms of average precision (AP) per category, which is the average of precision values computed at 10 Intersection over Union (IoU) thresholds (from 0.50 to 0.95 with a step of 0.05). The mean Average Precision (mAP) is the average AP over all the categories. A higher value of mAP corresponds to a detector with better localization.

Because the objects to be detected in the autonomous driving context appear in the scene at different sizes according to their distance from the ego-vehicle, it is useful to compute the average precision over small (AP_s), medium (AP_m), and large (AP_l) objects to quantify the effect of the distance from the ego-vehicle on detector’s performance. Small objects have a bounding box area smaller than 32^2 pixels, large objects have an area larger than 96^2 pixels, and medium objects have an area between 32^2 and 96^2 pixels, as proposed in the COCO challenge (Lin et al., 2014).

Evaluating the performance of MOT systems requires metrics that characterize the detection, localization, and association modules individually or globally. In the literature, different metrics have been pro-

posed for this scope (Guo et al., 2022b).

The MOTA (Multiple Object Tracking Accuracy) metric combines the counts of false positives (FP), false negatives (FN), identity switches (IDSw), and the number of ground truth objects (GT) to provide a holistic measure of tracking accuracy as defined in eq. 4.

$$\text{MOTA} = 1 - \frac{(\text{FP} + \text{FN} + \text{IDSw})}{\text{GT}} \quad (4)$$

The MOTP (Multiple Object Tracking Precision) metric measures the average overlap between the predicted and the ground-truth bounding boxes of correctly matched objects. MOTP quantifies the precision in the localization of the detected objects as defined in eq. 5, where TP is the number of true positives, p_i is the predicted bounding box, gt_i is the corresponding ground truth bounding box, and $\text{IoU}(p_i, gt_i)$ represents the Intersection over Union between the predicted and ground-truth bounding boxes.

$$\text{MOTP} = \frac{1}{TP} \sum_{i=1}^{TP} \text{IoU}(p_i, gt_i) \quad (5)$$

The association performance of the tracker is measured by the IDF1 score, which evaluates how well the tracker maintains consistent identities across frames. It is defined by eq. 6, where $IDTP$ is the number of identity true positives, $IDFP$ is the number of identity false positives, and $IDFN$ is the number of identity false negatives.

$$\text{IDF1} = \frac{2 \times IDTP}{2 \times IDTP + IDFP + IDFN} \quad (6)$$

Eventually, the HOTA (Higher Order Tracking Accuracy) metric (Luiten et al., 2021) measures both detection and association errors at different localization thresholds α allowing a more comprehensive evaluation of tracking systems, as defined in eq. 7. DetA measures the proportion of correctly detected objects over the total detected objects at a specific localization threshold, as in eq. 8. AssA quantifies the tracker’s ability to correctly associate detections over time, as defined by eq. 9, where TPA , FNA , and FPA represent true positive associations, false negative associations, and false positive associations, respectively.

$$\text{HOTA} \approx \frac{1}{19} \sum_{\alpha \in \{0.05, 0.1, \dots, 0.95\}} \sqrt{\text{DetA}_\alpha \times \text{AssA}_\alpha} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{DetA}_\alpha = \frac{TP}{TP + FN + FP} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{AssA}_\alpha = \frac{1}{TP} \sum_{c \in TP} \frac{|TPA(c)|}{|TPA(c)| + |FNA(c)| + |FPA(c)|} \quad (9)$$

Metrics were computed using the TETA metric evaluation script (Li et al., 2022).

4.3 Fine-Tuning of the Detector

In (Zhu et al., 2019), the authors provided a model of Faster R-CNN with attended residual blocks organized as the architecture described in Section 3.2, and trained on the COCO dataset (Lin et al., 2014), a large-scale dataset adopted for object detection tasks and with 91 object categories belonging to general purpose super-categories as animals, vehicles, indoor objects, etc. We fine-tuned this publicly available model on the training set of the BDD100K Object Detection training set to substitute it for the baseline Faster R-CNN used in the original QDTrack model. The fine-tuning procedure allowed the model to detect the eight classes of the BDD100K dataset that correspond to moving objects (traffic signs and lights were excluded), as proposed in the BDD100K challenge.

During training, images were augmented according to a multi-scale resizing strategy. We applied the RandomChoiceResize transformation, which randomly selects one scale from a predefined list of six target resolutions with the short edge in the range [640, 800] and the long edge up to 1333. In particular, the input image is resized so that its dimensions fit within the selected limits while preserving the original aspect ratio (i.e., both sides are scaled by the same factor). Corresponding bounding boxes, masks, and keypoints are scaled consistently. Moreover, horizontal flipping is introduced randomly during training to introduce variability. This procedure performs multi-scale training without geometric distortion, improving the model’s robustness to object size variation.

The Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) optimizer was employed with an initial learning rate of 0.02, consistent with the configuration used during the original training of the model. A learning rate schedule combining an initial warm-up phase and a dynamic reduction strategy was adopted to ensure stable optimization during fine-tuning. Specifically, during the first 500 iterations, the learning rate gradually increased to allow smooth adaptation of the pre-trained weights and to avoid abrupt parameter updates at the beginning of training. After the warm-up phase, the learning rate was dynamically adjusted through a ReduceOnPlateau scheduler, which reduced the learning rate whenever the mAP improvement was lower than 0.003 for two consecutive epochs.

The detector fine-tuning lasted 12 epochs, while minimizing a multi-task loss function that integrates classification and regression objectives (Ren et al., 2016).

Table 1: Detector performance on the BDD100K Object Detection validation set. The best results are in bold, the runner-up results are in italic.

Detector	$mAP(\%)$	$AP_{50}(\%)$	$AP_{70}(\%)$	$AP_s(\%)$	$AP_m(\%)$	$AP_L(\%)$
baseline	31.7	55.5	31.2	11.6	33.1	51.4
model-1111-dcn	33.7	57.6	33	<i>13</i>	35	53.9
model-1111	32.9	56.7	32.4	12.9	34.5	52.2
model-0010-dcn	33.6	57.6	33.2	13.1	34.7	53.9
model-0010	33.7	57.6	33	<i>13</i>	35	53.9

Table 2: Tracking performance on the BDD100K Multi-Object Tracking validation set. The best results are in bold, the runner-up results are in italic.

MOT system	TP	FP	FN	IDS _w	mMOTA	mMOTP	mIDF1	mHOTA	mDetA	mAssA
Baseline QDTrack	324'876	41'326	111'395	6193	36.57	71.12	<i>51.60</i>	41.35	35.10	49.65
QDTrack with model-1111-dcn	339'978	<i>60'611</i>	95'437	7399	37.96	71.30	51.67	41.42	35.14	49.96
QDTrack with model-1111	339'290	65'082	95'967	7557	37.12	71.04	50.90	40.64	34.59	48.75
QDTrack with model-0010-dcn	<i>339'606</i>	61'295	<i>95'802</i>	7406	<i>37.93</i>	<i>71.29</i>	51.53	<i>41.38</i>	35.13	<i>49.85</i>
QDTrack with model-0010	338'713	65'035	96'547	7554	36.46	71.02	50.52	40.40	34.21	48.79

4.4 Ablation Study

It has been shown in (Zhu et al., 2019) that, in an object detection task, the combination of a deformable convolution and a transformer module with the key content-only term (ϵ_3) achieves higher accuracy and lower computational overhead than a transformer attention module with the four terms. Moreover, the authors showed that it is more beneficial for object detection to exploit deformable convolution than a transformer model with the query content and the relative position term (ϵ_2).

Starting from these results, we have compared four implementations of Faster R-CNN detector, each of which has a different configuration of the attended residual blocks. The name assigned to each model makes explicit the activation and deactivation of each attention factor in the implementation of the transformer modules, e.g. 0010 denotes the activation of ϵ_3 and the deactivation of the other terms. The compared models are as follows:

- **model-1111-dcn:** the weights of the transformer module are determined by the four attention factors, as shown in eq. 2. The last three convolution layers of the bottleneck are substituted for DCNs.
- **model-1111:** the weights of the transformer module are determined by the four attention factors, as defined by eq. 2. DCNs are not used.
- **model-0010-dcn:** the weights of the transformer module are determined exclusively by the key content-only term (ϵ_3). The last three convolution layers of the bottleneck are substituted for DCNs.

- **model-0010:** the weights of the transformer module are determined exclusively by the key content-only term (ϵ_3). DCNs are not used.

All models were fine-tuned under identical training conditions, as described in Section 4.3.

5 RESULTS

Table 1 shows the detectors' performance in terms of the mean Average Precision computed on the BDD100K Object Detection validation set.

Table 2 summarizes the performance of the five MOT systems obtained by substituting the detector into QDTrack. The table shows the counts of matches, false positives, false negatives, and identity switches computed on the videos included in the BDD100K MOT validation set. Moreover, the table shows the holistic metrics proposed in Section 4.2 but computed as weighted means of per-class values. The results of the baseline QDTrack model were obtained using the official pre-trained weights released by the authors in (Pang et al., 2021). These weights correspond to the version of QDTrack originally trained and evaluated on the BDD100K dataset, ensuring a fair evaluation of the proposed modifications.

Table 3 reports the inference time and the frames per second, both averaged over the 200 videos of the BDD100K MOT validation set, computed on a NVIDIA GPU L40S. The table reports the number of parameters of each detector to estimate how the use of attention mechanisms increases the complexity of the network and, as a consequence, the RAM occupancy.

Table 3: Number of parameters, average inference time, and FPS for each MOT system. The last column reports the accuracy–efficiency trade-off of each system relative to the Baseline QDTrack.

MOT system	Detector’s parameters	Average Inference time (ms)	FPS	$\Delta mMOTA/\Delta time$
Baseline QDTrack	41’384’056	39.5	25.33	-
QDTrack with model-1111-dcn	47’872’363	56.2	17.80	+0.08
QDTrack with model-1111	47’291’521	54.3	18.40	+0.04
QDTrack with model-0010-dcn	45’509’995	43.2	23.13	+0.37
QDTrack with model-0010	44’929’153	40.7	24.54	-0.09

(a) Baseline QDTrack

(b) QDTrack with self-attention

Figure 2: Comparison of predictions between two MOT systems. Left: Baseline QDTrack; right: enhanced model. False positives are marked with a magenta star. Bounding box colors indicate the predicted class (red: pedestrian, orange: truck, blue: car, green: bicycle). The right subfigure is identical for QDTrack with model-0010-dcn or model-1111-dcn.

Figure 3: From left to right: ground truth, Baseline QDTrack predictions, and QDTrack with model-0010-dcn predictions. White bounding boxes indicate cars.

6 DISCUSSION

Introducing attended residual blocks in Faster R-CNN increases the mean average precision of the detector by 2%. Table 1 shows that the best detectors are model-1111-dcn and model-0010, whose performance is equivalent; both models reached the same value for the six average precision metrics. The detector model-0010-dcn is still better than the baseline one but shows worse performance on medium-sized objects compared to the two best detectors. However, the lower performance on medium-size objects entails a negligible decrease in the value mAP , which remains close to the value achieved by the best detectors.

Integrating the detectors into the QDTrack model allows us to evaluate how the attention mechanisms

contribute to the performance of the MOT system. Table 2 shows that attended residual blocks positively contribute to the performance of the MOT system by increasing the number of true positives and reducing the number of false negatives. In fact, taking the baseline QDTrack model as a reference, the increase in true positives varies between 4.26% and 4.65%, depending on the configuration of the attended residual blocks, while the decrease in false negatives varies between 13.32% and 14.33%. On the downside, it is possible to observe an increase in false positives and identity switches. Even though we observe an increase in both correct and wrong detections, the net effect is to improve the system performance. The difference between the number of true positives and the sum of errors (false positives, false negatives, and identity switches) increases by 54.25% and 45.37%

with the detectors model-1111-dcn and model-0010-dcn, respectively. The same difference increases by 19.85% and 15.28% with the detectors model-1111 and model-0010, respectively.

Moreover, Table 2 shows that the best MOT system is the one that combines QDTrack and the detector model-1111-dcn. In particular, mMOTA increases by 1.39 points compared to the baseline QDTrack, while all other metrics show a lower increase. The comparison of QDTrack with model-1111-dcn and the baseline QDTrack category by category reveals a decrease in the MOTA value for the class "car" (-1.8) but a significant increase for the categories "bicycle" (+6.9) and "bus" (+2.9). Interestingly, we observed that the number of false positives increases only for the class "car", while it decreases for all the other categories. The runner-up MOT system is the one based on model-0010-dcn, whose average MOTA increases by 1.36 compared to the baseline. The increment in false positives was observed only for the category "car", whose MOTA value decreases by 2.1 compared to the same value of the baseline. The QDTrack system with model-0010 is the only one that slightly worsens the baseline performance.

Figure 2 is an example of the improvement obtained by integrating the detector model-1111-dcn into QDTrack. The two subfigures, which show the same frame extracted from a video that belongs to the BDD100K data set, highlight with a magenta star on the bounding-boxes the false positives detected by the baseline QDTrack and the QDTrack with model-1111-dcn detector. The baseline model incorrectly recognizes two gasoline pumps as bicycle or truck while the QDTrack model enhanced with self-attention does not generate these two false positives.

Figure 3 shows another frame extracted from the BDD100K data set, where it is evident how beneficial the integration of self-attention in QDTrack is. The first subfigure highlights, with white bounding boxes, vehicles that are distant from the ego-vehicle and so close together that their headlights make it difficult to distinguish each one clearly. The baseline QDTrack model correctly detects one out of four vehicles but generates two false positives near the ego-vehicle. In contrast, QDTrack with model-0010-dcn correctly detects all four vehicles and generates only one false positive, caused by distant headlights that may be associated with another vehicle. Compared to the model using model-1111-dcn, this configuration produces one fewer false positive.

Table 3 shows that the adoption of attention mechanisms affects the average inference time of the MOT system. The system that reaches the best mMOTA value is the one with the longest average inference

time, which is 42.27% longer than the average inference time of the baseline system. The system with the second-best mMOTA value (QDTrack with model-0010-dcn) shows the best trade-off between the mMOTA value and the average inference time. In fact, the first and second best mMOTA values differ by only 0.03 points, while the average inference time of the second best system is 9.36% longer than the average inference time of the baseline system.

To better quantify the accuracy–efficiency trade-off, we computed the ratio $\Delta mMOTA/\Delta time$, expressing the gain in tracking accuracy per millisecond of additional inference time. Although the model-1111-dcn achieves the highest overall mMOTA (+1.39 points), its ratio $\Delta mMOTA/\Delta time$ of approximately 0.08 indicates a relatively high computational cost. In contrast, the model-0010-dcn achieves nearly the same accuracy improvement (+1.36 points) with only +3.7 ms of additional inference time, corresponding to a ratio of approximately 0.37, which means more than four times higher efficiency. This confirms that the deformable-convolution combined with the key-content-only attention configuration provides the best balance between accuracy and computational efficiency.

This result is consistent with what was observed in (Zhu et al., 2019), where the authors pinpointed that the combination of deformable convolution and the key-content-only term (ϵ_3) delivers the best accuracy-efficiency tradeoff.

7 CONCLUSIONS

Multi-object tracking algorithms are fundamental for self-driving systems in estimating the trajectories of moving objects on the road and to have reliable path planning and navigation. In this paper, we have integrated self-attention mechanisms into the detector of a state-of-the-art tracking-by-detection MOT to improve its performance. The results have shown that the adoption of attention mechanisms marginally increases the parameters of the network and the computation time while improving performance compared to the baseline system, especially in the less represented categories. The improvement is more evident on the MOTA metric, which is more related to the detector’s performance. In our future work, we plan to extend the method described in this paper to other detectors and tracking algorithms. Moreover, we plan to perform an end-to-end training of the detection-tracking pipeline to jointly optimize all the MOT’s components and improve the performance further, especially in terms of association.

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